

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABHIRAMI M R bearing USN 6SU19FS001 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABYMOL BINOY bearing USN 6SU19FS002 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ADITHYA P bearing USN 6SU19FS003 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ADITI NAGARAJ bearing USN 6SU19FS004 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms AKSHAYA bearing USN 6SU19FS005 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANUSHA bearing USN 6SU19FS006 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ARUN ROY bearing USN 6SU19FS007 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms DEVIKA M bearing USN 6SU19FS008 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms GANGA SURESH bearing USN 6SU19FS009 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms GOURI PARVATHI S bearing USN 6SU19FS010 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms K SHYAAM MOHAN bearing USN 6SU19FS011 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms LIJIN L bearing USN 6SU19FS012 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED ASLAM NASAR bearing USN 6SU19FS013 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms PEEYUSH S bearing USN 6SU19FS014 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms RAMSHIYA T T bearing USN 6SU19FS015 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms RITHUVARNA C bearing USN 6SU19FS016 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SCHUMACHER bearing USN 6SU19FS017 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHRAVYA S RAI bearing USN 6SU19FS018 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SIRKAZI MOHD FURQUAN MOHD FARHATH bearing USN 6SU19FS019 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SONA K bearing USN 6SU19FS020 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SREEHARI C K bearing USN 6SU19FS021 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SREEJA S bearing USN 6SU19FS022 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SUSHIN SAMUEL GEORGE bearing USN 6SU19FS023 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms TALUKH YANGFO bearing USN 6SU19FS024 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms THEERTHA M bearing USN 6SU19FS025 has completed his/her internship at Southern Detective agency Ernakulam in the first Semester of the Forensic Science programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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